

Srpsko hemijsko društvo

Serbian Chemical Society

**60. Savetovanje
Srpskog hemijskog društva**

**KRATKI IZVODI
RADOVA**

**60th Meeting of
the Serbian Chemical Society**

Book of Abstracts

**Niš 8. i 9. jun 2024. godine
Niš, Serbia, June 8-9, 2024**

CIP- Katalogizacija u publikaciji
Narodna biblioteka Srbije, Beograd

60. SAVETOVANJE SRPSKOG HEMIJSKOG DRUŠTVA

Niš, 8. i 9. jun 2024.

KRATKI IZVODI RADOVA

60th MEETING OF THE SERBIAN CHEMICAL SOCIETY

Niš, Serbia, 8-9 June 2024

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Izdaje/Published by

Srpsko hemijsko društvo/Serbian Chemical Society

Karnegijeva 4/III, 11000 Beograd, Srbija

tel./fax: +381 11 3370 467; www.shd.org.rs, E-mail: office@shd.org.rs

Za izdavača/For Publisher

Dušan Sladić, predsednik Srpskog hemijskog društva

Glavni i odgovorni urednik / Editor

Niko Radulović

Uređivački odbor / Editorial Board

Dušan Sladić, Niko Radulović

Priprema za štampu i štampa/Prepress and printing

Razvojno-istraživački centar grafičkog inženjerstva Tehnološko-metalurškog

fakulteta, Beograd / Research and Development Centre of Printing Engineering, Belgrade

Tiraž/ Circulation

20 primeraka / 20 copies printing

ISBN 978-86-7132-086-3

Naučni odbor

Scientific Committee

Niko Radulović, predsednik/chair

Dušan Sladić

Radomir Saičić

Ivanka Popović

Gordana Stojanović

Sanja Grgurić Šipka

Snežana Tošić

Tatjana Anđelković

Goran Roglić

Igor Pašti

Vidoslav Dekić

Vesna Mišković-Stanković

Maja Stanković

Milan Dekić

Marija Genčić

Marko Rodić

Aleksandar Oklješa

Boris Furtula

Dušica Rodić

Aleksandra Dapčević

Organizacioni odbor

Organising Committee

Marko Mladenović, predsednik/chair

Niko Radulović

Marija Genčić

Dragan Zlatković

Miljana Đorđević Zlatković

Milena Živković Stošić

Milan Nešić

Milica Nešić

Jelena Denić

Milan Dimitrijević

Dijana Jovanović

Danijela Nikolić

Luka Vasić

Savetovanje je podržalo / Supported by

Ministarstvo nauke, tehnološkog razvoja i inovacija Republike Srbije

Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of Republic of Serbia

Soft i hard korona mikroplastike u interakciji sa alergenom β -laktoglobulinom kravljeg mleka

Jelena M. Ćimović¹, Nikola Gligorijević², Mirjana Radomirović¹, Tamara Vasović¹,
Marija Stojadinović¹, Dragana Stanić-Vučinić¹, Tanja Ćirković Veličković^{1,3}

¹ Univerzitet u Beogradu, Hemijski fakultet, Katedra za biohemiju, Beograd, Srbija, ² Univerzitet u Beogradu, Institut za hemiju tehnologiju i metalurgiju, Centar za hemiju, Beograd, Srbija, ³ Srpska akademija nauka i umetnosti, Beograd, Srbija

Interakcija mikroplastike (MP) s proteinima stvara kompleks poznat kao proteinska korona. U okviru korone, MP dobija nove biološke osobine, uključujući izbegavanje imunog sistema, dugotrajnije zadržavanje u cirkulaciji i ometanje ćelijskih procesa. Formiranje biofilma na površini MP je višestepeni proces, gde se nakon prvobitnog vezivanja molekula s visokim afinitetom i formiranja čvrste korone, može razviti i labavija korona u kasnijim fazama. β -laktoglobulin (BLG), glavni protein u surutki kravljeg mleka, često korišćen u hrani, može izazvati značajne zdravstvene probleme kod osoba alergičnih na mleko. Ovo istraživanje je imalo za cilj da pruži bolji uvid u interakcije između BLG kao alergena hrane i odabranih MP (polietilen-tereftalat, PET, <80 μ m; polipropilen, PP, 63-180 μ m). Izolovani nepasterizovani/pasterizovani BLG je inkubiran s PP i PET *in vitro*, u simuliranim fiziološkim tečnostima, a formirane korone su analizirane SDS-PAGE elektroforezom pod redukujućim uslovima i densitometrijom. Rezultati pokazuju da BLG slabo vezuje za obe MP. Postoji razlika u proteinima čvrstih korona između pasterizovanog i nepasterizovanog BLG, kao i u proteinskom profilu korona PP i PET inkubiranih s pasterizovanim ili nepasterizovanim BLG. Naši rezultati ukazuju da prisustvo MP može uticati na biodostupnost i alergene osobine i pasterizovanog i nepasterizovanog BLG.

Soft and hard corona of microplastics interacted with allergenic bovine milk β -lactoglobulin

Jelena M. Ćimović¹, Nikola Gligorijević², Mirjana Radomirović¹, Tamara Vasović¹,
Marija Stojadinović¹, Dragana Stanić-Vučinić¹, Tanja Ćirković Veličković^{1,3}

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Chemistry, Department of Biochemistry, Belgrade, Serbia ² University of Belgrade, Institute of Chemistry, Technology and Metallurgy, Department of Chemistry, Belgrade, Serbia, ³ Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade, Serbia

Microplastics (MPs) interact with proteins, forming a complex called a protein corona. This corona alters the biological identity and properties of MPs, enabling them to evade the immune system, persist longer in circulation, and disrupt cellular and molecular processes. Biofilm formation on MPs occurs in several steps, starting with initial binding of molecules to form a hard corona, followed by the formation of a soft corona. β -Lactoglobulin (BLG), a major whey protein in bovine milk, is highly valued as a food ingredient but poses significant health risks to milk-allergic individuals. This study aimed to understand BLG's interactions with selected MPs (polyethylene terephthalate, PET, <80 μ m; polypropylene, PP, 63-180 μ m). BLG, isolated from unpasteurized/pasteurized milk, was incubated with PP and PET in simulated physiological fluids. The resulting coronas were analyzed using reduced SDS-PAGE electrophoresis and densitometry. BLG exhibited low binding to both MPs, with pasteurized BLG showing the lowest binding to PP (less than 1% of control in its soft corona). There were differences in the protein content of hard coronas between pasteurized and unpasteurized BLG, with a slightly higher percentage of bound proteins in the hard corona of unpasteurized BLG. Additionally, the protein profile of hard coronas differed between PET and PP incubated with pasteurized BLG compared to those with unpasteurized BLG. These findings suggest that the presence of MPs may affect the bioavailability and allergenic properties of both pasteurized and unpasteurized BLG.

Acknowledgment: This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 965173, IMPTOX. This study was supported and funded by the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia, grant number 451-03-66/2024-03/200168 signed with UBFC